

Baltic MUPPETS

**Baltic
MUPPETS**

DELIVERABLE 6.3

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Baltic MUPPETS is a three-year project funded by the Interregional Innovation Investment (I3) Instrument. The project aims to create a new value chain for small mussels (1-3 cm) from the Baltic Sea by developing high-value pet food products.

This document presents the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the project, as defined in the Grant Agreement. This DMP provides guidelines for the partners to follow and should be updated with specific information on Baltic MUPPETS data sets throughout the project. The DMP includes a summary of the data that will be collected under the different Work Packages and how the Baltic MUPPETS project will adopt a FAIR data policy through several guidelines and documents by widely accepted frameworks and guidelines.

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ACRONYMS

BSR	Baltic Sea Region
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
EAB	External Advisory Board
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
I3	Interregional Innovation Investment Instrument
IP	Intellectual Property
M	Month
PC	Project Coordinator
PSG	Project Steering Group
PP	Project Partner(s)
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package

INTRODUCTION

Due to low salinity, Baltic Sea mussels are often smaller and, therefore, not always suitable for the human consumption market. In the western Baltic Sea, small mussels are considered a side-stream of market-size mussel production. Baltic MUPPETS is a three-year project funded under the Interregional Innovation Investment (I3) Instrument and aims to create a new value chain for small mussels in the Baltic Sea Region (BSR) by developing high-value and healthy pet food products.

The project will invest in innovative submerged farming, harvesting and processing technologies, contributing to local economic growth and quality employment opportunities. Besides the socioeconomic benefits, mussel farming will provide a range of ecosystem services such as nutrient removal, improved water quality, and increased biodiversity.

The present document outlines the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) developed for Baltic MUPPETS as part of the WP6 Communication, dissemination, and exploitation of results.

The DMP outlines the ways in which data is collected, generated and/or processed throughout the lifespan of the project. The DMP will facilitate the potential re-use of the data collected and processed and outputs produced within the project. In the first six months of the project, an Initial DMP is prepared (D6.3) with the involvement of all project partners (PP) filling in the table that was created based on the Horizon Europe DMP template (see Annex I) specifying datasets per work package/tasks and their most important characteristics in line with the FAIR principles: findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable to ensure the data collected and processed under the project comply with these. Both the table and the DMP will be regularly updated, and the final DMP will be delivered before the end of the project.

1. DATA SUMMARY

In the Baltic MUPPETS project, data is defined as information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings, images, and maps. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form (European Commission, 2016). Therefore, data are defined as facts, documented perceptions, and statistics collected for reference or analysis. Data can take different forms, written, visual, audio, spatial reference, or others. Data is collected, named, stored, analyzed, compiled, and managed and may also be compiled into digital outputs.

Baltic MUPPETS will use existing data as much as possible. Existing qualitative and quantitative data in numerical, visual, and textual from diverse sources will be compiled in different work packages, such as WP1 Prepare market and sustainable business for scale-up, WP2 Mussel Farming, WP3 Mussel processing & logistics, WP4 Pet-food product development

& marketing and serve as input for WP5 Third-party Financing and WP6 Communication, dissemination, and exploitation of results.

The Baltic MUPPETS project will produce data products and scenarios for mussel farming, harvesting and processing, product development, and market access. Reports, methods, and updated open-source models and tools will all be publicly available. Moreover, dissemination and communication outputs may also be considered under digital products such as brochures, journal articles, presentations, webinars, website content, and news items.

It is also expected that the project will produce videos that will be posted on the project website and disseminated through social media activities.

Webinars and meeting recordings may also be made public and uploaded to the website. In this case, the invitation to a recorded meeting includes a disclaimer for the consent of participants.

Each WP leader is responsible for the data management of their WP.

A detailed list of datasets per Work Package identified in the initial stage of the project, with the most critical information based on the HE DMP template, can be found in Annex I.

Foreseen project outputs

Written outputs

- **Examples:** Articles, Reports, Manuals, Guidance etc.
- **Description:** The project will produce several project reports which will be made publicly available. The project will also produce peer-reviewed research articles, manuals, brochures, and flyers. They will be widely disseminated to various target groups via the project website, social media and by linking with other multipliers.
- **Number of foreseen written outputs:** At least 10.

Presentations

- **Examples:** Oral Presentation, Posters, Performance, Media output
- **Description:** The project will produce several presentations and posters for conferences and online events. This will also include oral presentations and videos (i.e. recorded interviews with project partners). Such presentations and videos will also be made available via the project website.
- **Number of foreseen written outputs:** At least 15

Conferences

- **Description:** The project will hold one major conference towards the end of the project and several workshops and webinars throughout the project. The project partners will also attend and present at conferences, workshops, and webinars. When possible, a stand for the project will also be organised to share the project results and dissemination material (i.e. flyers). The project will aim to organise and co-organise

workshops and meetings at or back-to-back with major international conferences to reach stakeholders and maximise impacts.

- **Number of foreseen outputs:** At least 15

Datasets

- **Description:** Given that the project has just started, it cannot be foreseen at this stage exactly how many datasets the project may produce. The data will be collected for all the project deliverables. Thus, there may be different data sets (such as initial data baseline, assessment results, gap analysis, ecological and economic criteria, spatial scenario data and maps).
- The databases will initially be kept internal, but where relevant, may be shared with the wider community. Additionally, relevant data and information will be compiled and summarised into respective deliverables which will be publicly available.
- **The data and information will be collected:** through desk research (i.e. literature review) and data collection (i.e. monitoring data from the mussel farms). Datasets from past projects where partners were involved may also be used.
- **Number of foreseen outputs:** At least 15

Online outputs

- **Description:** The Baltic MUPPETS webpage is also being produced during the project. The page is expected to last well beyond the lifetime of the project. The final outputs of the project will be hosted on the website. Moreover, the project newsletter will also be produced and released at least three times. The project website will serve as a repository for the project data and outputs not subject to IPR or GDPR, where they will be available with an Open-Source approach, i.e. as open as possible, as closed as necessary during and after the lifetime of the project. The SUBMARINER Network webpage will serve as a repository too if necessary.
- **Number of foreseen outputs:** website +3 project Newsletters

Table 1: List of Deliverables

D	Deliverable Name	WP No	Lead Partner	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Month
D1.1	Business and investment plan	WP1	9 - CRM	R - Document, report	PU - Public	36
D1.2	Report on the implementation of the business investments belonging to the portfolio	WP1	9 - CRM	R - Document, report	PU - Public	36
D1.3	Assessment of the market readiness	WP1	9 - CRM	R - Document, report	PU - Public	36
D1.4	List of the remaining bottlenecks	WP1	9 - CRM	R - Document, report	PU - Public	36
D1.5	Report on sustainability of mussel farming and production of pet-food, and on value of ecosystem services	WP1	1 - SUBNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	24
D2.1	Deployment of two full-scale mussel farms	WP2	2- SEA	DEC - Websites, patent	PU - Public	21
D2.2	Two site specific production manuals	WP2	8 - BLR	DEC - Websites, patent	PU - Public	36
D3.1	Machinery in place and mussel meal produced	WP3	4 - BSF	DEC - Websites, patent	PU - Public	12
D3.2	Hygienization process identified and tested	WP3	3 - ECO	DATA - data sets, m m	PU - Public	18
D3.3	Plant experiment results	WP3	3 - ECO	DATA - data sets, m m	PU - Public	18
D4.1	2 Products developed	WP4	3 - ECO	DEM - Demonstrator,	PU - Public	36
D4.2	1 Product ready to be launched	WP4	3 - ECO	DEM - Demonstrator,	SEN - Sensitive	36
D4.3	A report on German market possibilities	WP4	5 - KMF	R - Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	36
D5.1	Open call documents Kit & third-party financing rules	WP5	11 - F6S	OTHER	PU - Public	7
D6.1	Stakeholder Database, Communication Strategy, and Plan	WP6	1 - SUBNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	3
D6.2	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results	WP6	1 - SUBNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	3
D6.3	Knowledge and Data Management Plan	WP6	1 - SUBNET	OTHER	PU - Public	6
D6.4	An onsite study visit to Västervik region	WP6	2- SEA	OTHER	PU - Public	20
D6.5	An onsite study visit to Kiel region	WP6	5 - KMF	OTHER	PU - Public	34
D6.6	An onsite study visit to Danish region	WP6	6 - WIS	OTHER	SEN - Sensitive	28
D6.7	A final conference and exhibition in Kiel	WP6	1 - SUBNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	34
D7.1	Minutes of the general meetings complemented with information	WP7	1 - SUBNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	6
D7.2	Minutes of the general meetings complemented with information	WP7	1 - SUBNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	12
D7.3	Minutes of the general meetings complemented with information	WP7	1 - SUBNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	18
D7.4	Minutes of the general meetings complemented with information	WP7	1 - SUBNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	24
D7.5	Minutes of the general meetings complemented with information	WP7	1 - SUBNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	30
D7.6	Minutes of the general meetings complemented with information	WP7	1 - SUBNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	35

A list of the main foreseen outputs per each task/Work Package in the Baltic MUPPETS project is available in Annex I.

2. DATA COLLECTION OBJECTIVES

The main purpose of data collection under the Baltic MUPPETS project is to analyze environmental and economic data and criteria regarding mussel farming in the Baltic Sea region. Some new data will be collected such as monitoring data from the three participating mussel farms in Sweden, Denmark, and Germany. Still, existing data will also be reused, as well as information from stakeholders involved in the Communities of Practice (CoPs). Finally, dissemination and communication outputs will be generated as digital products such as brochures, journal articles, presentations, and webinar documentation, as well as the website content and news items.

3. TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA

The Baltic MUPPETS project works with three different mussel farms that have their own in-situ types of data collected for different purposes. This ranges from marine biodiversity data to economic sector-related data. This data will be collected/compiled from different existing repositories and reused for the purpose of the project. This means that there are plenty of types of data to be acquired. This data will create outputs of the project, such as reports, manuals, models/scenarios/GIS outputs, guidance, reviews, etc.

Also, personal data will be collected for members of the consortium, members of the CoPs, External Advisory Board, such as name, affiliation, country, mailing address, expertise/professional background, job title, and photo.

A preliminary list of data types to be collected/compiled in the project for each individual deliverable/output produced per task is given in Annex I. The list will be updated throughout the duration of the project.

4. RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA

The project will review, compile and re-use available datasets from multiple sources and collected data within the project will serve as input for the other work packages.

No large size data are expected to be generated nor re-used.

Additional information on the re-used data can be found in Annex I and will be updated at a later stage as this is still to be defined and updated throughout the project.

5. ORIGIN OF DATA

Data origin for both re-used or generated data is dataset specific. It is mostly open-access data, open-access geospatial datasets (from national, international, and EU infrastructures), free internet sources, literature repositories (e.g. Web of Science), grey literature and documents, ecological/biological datasets from data sharing platforms and public repositories.

6. DATA UTILITY

Baltic MUPPETS data will be useful to other projects working on related topics – there are several EU projects dealing with the Baltic Sea region and mussel cultivation-related issues. But first, it is expected that data and outputs generated during the project implementation will be used by key users and beneficiaries, such as SMEs, coastal planners, policymakers, researchers, and governance authorities.

7. FAIR DATA

“The FAIR Data Principles are a set of guiding principles in order to make data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable” (Wilkinson et al., 2016). This chapter explains how the Baltic MUPPETS project will adhere to all components of the FAIR data policy. As the project progresses, data set elements will be added to the data management plan and checked with the FAIR data principles.

Findable Data

Data must be findable and retrievable over prolonged periods. Therefore, metadata files and standardized identification mechanisms are required where metadata are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier; data are described with rich metadata, and metadata are registered or indexed in a searchable resource (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

The project outputs will be described with standard metadata, and DOIs will be assigned. Where relevant and feasible, Baltic MUPPETS will ensure the data storage and archival of project outputs in open-access targeted e-infrastructures such as Zenodo.

Accessible Data

To make data accessible means that corresponding metadata are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol; the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable; the protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure where necessary; and metadata are accessible, even when data are no longer available (Wilkinson et al., 2016). The Baltic MUPPETS project follows the Horizon Europe guidelines to the rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020 (EC Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, 2017).

The project outputs will be publicly available with open access, available also on the project's website, in line with GDPR rules, unless it is data that is commercially sensitive or protected by Intellectual Property Rights rights (IPR).

Interoperable Data

Interoperable data means that (meta)data use is formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation; metadata are released with a clear and accessible data usage license; (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles; (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data (Wilkinson et al., 2016). Making data interoperable is linked to making data re-usable and accessible.

Baltic MUPPETS will use existing standards, formats and vocabularies for data and metadata. In terms of data management, if there is a need for a specific open format or data requirement from the users, the standards can be adjusted to specific needs enhancing impact.

Reusable Data

The data will be made available to the public, and its re-use will be encouraged. The use of open data and software licenses for data sharing and re-use, such as Creative Commons or Open Data Commons, will be considered.

While the aim is to have all the data and project results publicly available in line with the protection of Intellectual Property Rights, an IPR agreement will be established in the project to ensure that innovation and competitiveness are maximised. All publications and reports will be made available to the public either through the project's website (for technical reports, progress reports, and non-peer-reviewed literature) or open-access facilities (for peer-reviewed publications).

Where relevant and feasible, Baltic MUPPETS will ensure the data storage and archival of project outputs in open-access targeted e-infrastructures such as Zenodo.

8. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

All costs related to data management that will occur during the project implementation will be covered by the project budget. The long-term maintenance of the Baltic MUPPETS website and its content, including all the listed data and outputs, will be ensured, and financially covered by SUBMARINER Network for five years after the project ends.

The project coordinator responsible for the development of the Data Management Plan – Lead Partner Submariner NETWORK has assigned Annette Heiß to be a dedicated Data Management Officer responsible for data management and quality assurance.

All project partners will ensure that the data they collect, produce, handle, and store are in line with the DMP and will appoint a contact person responsible within their institution.

9. DATA SECURITY

Privacy

Some of the project data contains sensitive or proprietary information or confidential data as per General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). In the case of such data, options such as anonymisation or aggregation will be considered when participants have a better overview of the data to try to make it available. If that is not possible, the data will not be made publicly available.

Data Security

For data security and storage, different options are being explored in the Baltic MUPPETS project. Currently, data and information are kept in the Microsoft TEAMS repository created for the purpose of the project, to which the partners have access.

Ethical Aspects

Baltic MUPPETS upholds the following ethical principles: the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy, the right to protection of personal data, the right to physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination, and the need to ensure high levels of human health protection. Based on these principles, data protection measures in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) are set up.

10. UPDATE OF INITIAL DMP

The initial Data Management Plan was based on the HE Template and Excel tables filled in by Baltic MUPPETS partners per WP, which is in Annex I of the Initial DMP. The table, as well as the Initial DMP, will be updated regularly during the project implementation until completing the Final Data Management Plan in M34.

REFERENCES

Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template, Version 1.0, 05 May 2021

Wilkinson et al., 2016: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship; <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618> (accessed: 15.05.2023)

ANNEXES

Annex I: Table form containing questions from HE DMP template to be filled in by project partners – to be continuously updated throughout the project

	Output	Dataset/Item	Re-used data	Origin of data reused	Produced data	Progress	Data utility	Metadata created	Type of metadata created and how	Metadata standards	Storage	Archiving	Other data infrastructure	Identifier type (specify if results are already clear, otherwise will be updated later)	Tools & version used
WP1	Name of the output	Name of the dataset/item	Name of the reused data	Provenance	Name of the produced data	Planned/in prep./finished	Define usefulness outside of your project /other WP	Yes/No	Depending on the tools applied and repository	Depending on the tools applied and repository	Where you are going to put your data short-term	Where you are going to put your data long-term (such as Zenodo)	If your data will be in other data infrastructures, indicate which one (such as EMODnet)	e.g. DOI	For data collection and data analysis
T1.1/T3.4	D 1.1 Market analysis for food ingredients in pet food	Identify petfeed producers in Germany	no	na	List	finished	All WPs within Baltic Muppets	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		Analyse petfeed producer demand and production capacities	no	na	Data set	in prep.	WP 3	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		Questionnaire for petfood producers	no	na	Data set	ongoing	All WPs within Baltic Muppets	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		Customer interviews	no	na	Data set	in prep.	All WPs within Baltic Muppets	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		Personel interviews	no	na	Data set	in prep.	All WPs within Baltic Muppets	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		Assessment of the market readiness	no	na	Report	planned	All WPs within Baltic Muppets	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		Possibilities to introduce products to the German Market	no	na	List	planned	All WPs within Baltic Muppets	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
T1.2	D 1.2. Business Cases	Production potential in the central baltic	Plan your farm	http://www.sea.ee/bbg-odss/Map/MapMain	Written documents	in prep.	All WPs within Baltic Muppets	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		Critical mass for export of small mussels to Swedish site	no		Data set	planned	WP 3.1	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		Business and investment plan	no		Written documents	in prep.	All WPs within Baltic Muppets				CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		List of remaining bottlenecks	no		Written documents	planned	WP 1				CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
T1.3	D 1.3. Regulation Report	Update of BBG Report	Legislation issues of mussel farming in the Baltic Sea by Y. Rössner	Baltic Blue Growth Project	Written documents	in prep.	WP 3	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		Map regulating authorities in the participating countries			List	planned	All WPs within Baltic Muppets				CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
		Food Security aspects	EU directives	EFSA	Written documents	planned	All WPs within Baltic Muppets	No			CRM Computer, s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			
T1.4	Digital maps for siting new mussel farms and assessing mussel production in the Baltic Sea region	Datasets linking mussel growth to nitrogen, phosphorus and carbon uptake by farmed mussels	Copernicus ocean data products (BALTICSEA_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_03_006, BALTICSEA_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_BIO_003_007 and BALTICSEA_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_WAV_03_010) are used as input for spatial models	Copernicus data portal; Baltic Blue Growth Project	Spatial maps of growth, nitrogen, phosphorus and carbon uptake by cultured mussels	planned	The maps produced make it possible to maximise production yields while respecting the carrying capacity of the environment. Such data will also make it possible to quantify how much shellfish farms can be expected to recycle nutrients and carbon, thereby contributing to various sustainability and climate change mitigation targets.	No	Not relevant	Not relevant	The data is stored on the University of Tartu server (https://gis.sea.ee/); this server is used to provide the data to the ODSS decision support tool (i.e. it is downloadable for all).	Not relevant	The data is stored on the University of Tartu server (https://gis.sea.ee/).	Not relevant	Map layers are generated using the Dynamic Energy Budget modelling technique
T1.5	D 1.5 Sustainability Report	Cost-benefit-Analysis	Other WP inputs/literature review	various sources	Written documents	in prep.	All WPs within Baltic Muppets/ decision makers/ authorities / researchers				s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	to be defined			Standard software (MS office, Adobe)

	Output	Accessibility	If not open, state the reason	Keywords	Findability	Interoperability of data/research outputs	Data exchange	Data type	Format	size (MB)	insert name and organization of the contact within the project per each data set	
WP1	Name of the output	Open/not open		To describe your dataset	Depending on the repository	Depending on the repository, formats and standards in use	Depending on the repository	Such as a map, text, a model etc.	Such as jpg, png, shp, pdf etc.			
T1.1/T3.4	D 1.1 Market analysis for food ingredients in pet food	Open		Petfeed producers in Germany	easy			List	pdf	12,1 kB	CRM - Peter Krost	
		open		Producer demand	easy			Report	pdf		CRM - Peter Krost	
		not open	IP; Commercially sensitive			na						CRM - Peter Krost
		not open	IP; Commercially sensitive			na						CRM - Peter Krost
		not open	IP; Commercially sensitive			na						CRM - Peter Krost
		open		Market readiness	easy			Report	pdf			CRM - Peter Krost
		not open	IP			na						
T1.2	D 1.2. Business Cases	open		Production potential	easy			Report	pdf		CRM - Peter Krost	
		open		Critical mass	easy			Report	pdf		CRM - Peter Krost	
		open		Business and investment plan	easy			Report	pdf		CRM - Peter Krost	
		not open			na							CRM - Peter Krost
T1.3	D 1.3. Regulation Report	open		legal aspects	easy						CRM - Peter Krost	
		open		authority matrix	easy						CRM - Peter Krost	
											CRM - Peter Krost	
T1.4	Digital maps for siting new mussel farms and assessing mussel production in the Baltic Sea region	open	Not relevant	Baltic Sea, farmed mussel growth, farmed mussel nutrient sequestration, farmed mussel carbon capture, farming carrying capacity	Data can be found via the ODSS portal	Data is shared in the ODSS data portal using web and feature maps services; alternatively, data can be downloaded as simple cvs files	Data can be freely downloaded from the ODSS porta	Digital Map	Data is stored in ArcGIS geodatabases, but is available as web and feature map services, and can also be downloaded as csv files.	Not yet known	Merli Rätsep (University of Tartu)	
T1.5	D 1.5 Sustainability Report	open		cost-benefit analysis, mussel farming				Digital report	pdf		Jean-Baptiste Thomas, Annette Heiss (SUBMARINER Network)	

	Output	Dataset/Item	Re-used data	Origin of data reused	Produced data	Progress	Data utility	Metadata created	Type of metadata created and how	Metadata standards	Storage	Archiving	Other data infrastructure
WP2	Name of the output	Name of the dataset/item	Name of the reused data	Provenance	Name of the produced data	Planned/in prep./finished	Define usefulness outside of your project /other WP	Yes/No	Depending on the tools applied and repository	Depending on the tools applied and repository	Where you are going to put your data short-term	Where you are going to put your data long-term (such as Zenodo)	If your data will be in other data infrastructures, indicate which one (such as EMODnet)
T2.1	D.2.1	Video of full scale farms with english subtitles	No		Video	Planned	Public information	Yes			s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	Ecopelag Sharepoint	
T2.2	M6 Optimized harvest system - Data report	cost of harvest system	No		Report	Planned	No (Yes: other WP)				Ecopelag Sharepoint	Ecopelag Sharepoint	
T2.3													
T2.4													
T2.5	M4	time of harvesting, worktime, cost of personell,harvest amount, biomass	No		Report	Planned							
	M5	Summary of monitoring and lab data - Blr	No		Data report	Planned	No	Yes	Coordinates, Depth, Date....		s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	Ecopelag Sharepoint, Wittrup, KMF, Submariner, Blue Research	
T2.6	M7	Two site specific production manuals Blr	No		Manual	Planned	No (Yes: other WP)				s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	Ecopelag Sharepoint, Wittrup, Blue Research	
	D.2.2	2 reports of 30 p in Swedish and Danish,	No		Report	Planned	Public information				tbd	tbd	
T2.7	NEW	Activity 1.3 - CRM. Raw data from SEA; KMF, WIS	No		Data report	Planned	Public information				s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	Ecopelag Sharepoint, Wittrup, KMF	

	Output	Identifier type (specify if results are already clear, otherwise will be updated later)	Tools & version used	Accessibility	If not open, state the reason	Keywords	Findability	Interoperability of data/research outputs	Data exchange	Data type	Format	size (MB)	Insert name and organization of the contact within the project per each data set
WP2	Name of the output	e.g. DOI	For data collection and data analysis	Open/not open		To describe your dataset	Depending on the repository	Depending on the repository, formats and standards in use	Depending on the repository	Such as a map, text, a model etc	Such as jpg, png, shp, pdf etc		
T2.1	D.2.1			Open		Mussel farming, Baltic Sea, Baltic Muppets, Aquaculture, Ecopelag	Easy		copyright	motion picture			Martin Reutgard
T2.2	M6 Optimized harvest system - Data report			Not open	IP					Text	.pdf		Martin Reutgard
T2.3													
T2.4													
T2.5	M4												
	M5		According to monitoring and lab manual	Not open	Research publication?					Text	.xlsx		Per Dolmer, Martin Reutgard, Rasmus Wittrup, Tim Staufenberg
T2.6	M7			Not open	IP					Text	.pdf		Ecopelag, Wittrup, Blr
	D.2.2			Open		Mussel farming, Baltic Sea, Baltic Muppets, Aquaculture, Ecopelag, Manual	Easy		copyright	Text	.pdf		Ecopelag, Wittrup, Blr
T2.7	NEW			Open						Text	.doc		Martin Reutgard, Rasmus Wittrup, Tim Staufenberg

	Output	Dataset/Item	Re-used data	Origin of data reused	Produced data	Progress	Data utility	Metadata created	Type of metadata created and how	Metadata standards	Storage	Archiving	Other data infrastructure	identifier type (specify if results are already clear, otherwise will be updated later)
WP3	Name of the output	Name of the dataset/item	Name of the reused data	Provenance	Name of the produced data	Planned/in prep./finished	Define usefulness outside of your project /other WP	Yes/No	Depending on the tools applied and repository	Depending on the tools applied and repository	Where you are going to put your data short-term	Where you are going to put your data long-term (such as Zenodo)	If your data will be in other data infrastructures, indicate which one (such as EMODnet)	e.g. DOI
T3.1	M8	Complete mussel meal line - Procurement documents/offers			Procurement	Finished	Other WPs				Ecopelag Sharepoint	Ecopelag Sharepoint		
	M10	Production line approved - Official factory permits for production start			Permits	in prep	Other WPs				Ecopelag Sharepoint	Ecopelag Sharepoint		
	D3.1	Video documentation of the mussel meal production line			Video	Planned	Public information	Yes			s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	Ecopelag Sharepoint		
T3.2														
T3.3	D3.2	Hygienization process identified and tested - Data showing that waste material reaches minimum requirements for the market			Data set	in prep	Public information	Yes			s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	Ecopelag Sharepoint		
	M12	Plant experiment with mussel shells - Evaluation report (Third party)			Report	Planned	Other WPs	Yes			tbd	tbd		
	D3.3	Plant experiment results - Evaluation report (Third party)			Data set	Planned	Public information	Yes			s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	Ecopelag Sharepoint		
T3.4	possible products from mussel shell	Valorisation of mussel shell as a side-stream			Data set	in prep.	Other WPs				s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	CAU Next Cloud		
	Nutritional value and chemical content	Lab tests on mussel meat (small mussels)			Data set	in prep.	Other WPs				s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	CAU Next Cloud		

	Output	Tools & version used	Accessibility	If not open, state the reason	Keywords	Findability	Interoperability of data/research outputs	Data exchange	Data type	Format	size (MB)	Insert name and organization of the contact within the project per each data set
WP3	Name of the output	For data collection and data analysis	Open/not open		To describe your dataset	Depending on the repository	Depending on the repository, formats and standards in use	Depending on the repository	Such as a map, text, a model etc	Such as jpg, png, shp, pdf etc		
T3.1	M8											Martin Karlsson
	M10											Martin Karlsson
	D3.1		Open		Mussel processing, Baltic Sea, Baltic Muppets, Aquaculture, Ecopelag	Easy		copyright	Video			Martin Karlsson
T3.2												Martin Karlsson
T3.3	D3.2		Open		ABP cat 3 hygienization, mussels composting, Baltic Muppets	Easy		copyright	text	.xlsx		Martin Karlsson
	M12			IP					text	.pdf		Martin Karlsson
	D3.3		Open		Fertilizer, mussel shells, plant experiment, mussel composting	Easy		copyright	text	.pdf		Martin Karlsson
T3.4	possible products from mussel shell		not open	IP	sid-streams, mussel shell				text	pdf		Rasha Shtay
	Nutritional value and chemical content		not open	IP	small mussels, marine resources, alternative proteins					pdf		Rasha Shtay

	Output	Dataset/Item	Re-used data	Origin of data reused	Produced data	Progress	Data utility	Metadata created	Type of metadata created and how	Metadata standards	Storage	Archiving	Other data infrastructure
WP4	Name of the output	Name of the dataset/item	Name of the reused data	Provenance	Name of the produced data	Planned/in prep./finished	Define usefulness outside of your project /other WP	Yes/No	Depending on the tools applied and repository	Depending on the tools applied and repository	Where you are going to put your data short-term	Where you are going to put your data long-term (such as Zenodo)	If your data will be in other data infrastructures, indicate which one (such as EMODnet)
T4.1 (D4.1 +M14)	two recipes one for cat food one for dog food	Specifications do ingredient lists and date on composition of Petfood, plan is to do 2 variety's			Report and data sets of different variables for production of petfood,	in prep.	during product development limited to WP4 participants, after development (M14) available for other partners				s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	CAU Next Cloud, Ecopelag Sharepoint	
T4.2, D4.2	Product ready for launch	information about first tests	literature review Other WP inputs/literature review		report on feedback from customers test group, satisfaction and experiences	Planned	Other WPs				s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	CAU Next Cloud, Ecopelag Sharepoint	
T4.3, M13	Contract manufacturers in place	Contract	Data from WP 1		Contract, Protocol on Selection and evaluation of manufacturere	Planned	Limited to WP4 partners. Not shared on public websites, but partly official at request				Ecopelag Sharepoint	Ecopelag Sharepoint	
T4.4, D4.3	Moved to T1.1, aubchapter	Report on knowledge gained and possibilities to integrate Swedish system and findings into German market			Digital report (english)	Planned	Public?				s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams		
T4.5	Internal certification	traceability of product, environmental safety datasets	Data from WP3		Permit applications, internal business system	in prep.	Limited to WP4 partners. Not shared on public websites.				Ecopelag Sharepoint	Ecopelag Sharepoint	
	Externa certification	traceability of product, environmental safety datasheets	Data from WP3		Permits, product specifications	Planned	Limited to WP4 partners. Not shared on public websites, but partly official at request				Ecopelag Sharepoint	Ecopelag Sharepoint	Database of the controlling agency
	labeling	Nutritional content list			Data set	planned	Public				s.Pro - Sustainable projects GmbH - Teams	CAU Next Cloud	

	Output	identifier type (specify if results are already clear, otherwise will be updated later)	Tools & version used	Accessibility	If not open, state the reason	Keywords	Findability	Interoperability of data/research outputs	Data exchange	Data type	Format	size (MB)	Insert name and organization of the contact within the project per each data set
WP4	Name of the output	e.g. DOI	For data collection and data analysis	Open/not open		To describe your dataset	Depending on the repository	Depending on the repository, formats and standards in use	Depending on the repository	Such as a map, text, a model etc	Such as jpg, png, shp, pdf etc		
T4.1 (D4.1 +M14)	two recipes one for cat food one for dog food			not open	IP on future products and basis for recipes	pet food, small mussels, marine resources				text	pdf, jpg		Rasha Shtay (CAU), Martin Karlsson (ECO)
T4.2, D4.2	Product ready for launch			open		sustainable, innovative products				text	pdf		Martin Karlsson (ECO)
T4.3, M13	Contract manufacturers in place			not public	IP of partners								Martin Karlsson (ECO)
T4.4, D4.3	Moved to T1.1, aubchapter									text	doc.		Martin Karlsson (ECO)
T4.5	Internal certification			not public						text	.pdf		Martin Karlsson (ECO)
	External certification			open but not public						text	.pdf		Martin Karlsson (ECO)
	labeling			open						text	pdf, jpg		Rasha Shtay (CAU)

	Output	Dataset/Item	Re-used data	Origin of data reused	Produced data	Progress	Data utility	Metadata created	Type of metadata created and how	Metadata standards	Storage	Archiving	Other data infrastructure	Identifier type (specify if results are already clear, otherwise will be updated later)
WP6	Name of the output	Name of the dataset/Item	Name of the reused data	Provenance	Name of the produced data	Planned/in prep./finished	Define usefulness outside of your project /other WP	Yes/No	Depending on the tools applied and repository	Depending on the tools applied and repository	Where you are going to put your data short-term	Where you are going to put your data long-term (such as Zenodo)	If your data will be in other data infrastructures, indicate which one (such as EMODnet)	e.g. DOI
T6.1	Stakeholder Database	Stakeholder Database	existing stakeholder database	SUBMARINER Network	stakeholder database	ongoing	for other WP	No			Sharepoint	Sharepoint		
T6.3	Community of Practice	Registration and participation lists of working groups	none	-	participation list	ongoing	only internal use	No			Sharepoint	Sharepoint		
T6.4	Online platform (Blue Bioeconomy Hub)	User data	none	-	user data	in prep	only internal use	No			Sharepoint	Sharepoint		
T6.5	Study visits and final conference	Registration and participation lists	none	-	participation list	in prep	only internal use	No			Sharepoint	Sharepoint		

	Output	Tools & version used	Accessibility	If not open, state the reason	Keywords	Findability	Interoperability of data/research outputs	Data exchange	Data type	Format	size (MB)	Insert name and organization of the contact within the project per each data set
WP6	Name of the output	For data collection and data analysis	Open/not open		To describe your dataset	Depending on the repository	Depending on the repository, formats and standards in use	Depending on the repository	Such as a map, text, a model etc	Such as jpg, png, shp, pdf etc		
T6.1	Stakeholder Database		not open	sensitive personal data					Excel list	.xls		Annette Heiss (SUBMARINER Network)
T6.3	Community of Practice		not open	sensitive personal data					Jot form, Excel list	.xls		Annette Heiss (SUBMARINER Network)
T6.4	Online platform (Blue Bioeconomy Hub)		not open	sensitive personal data					Excel list	.xls		Annette Heiss (SUBMARINER Network)
T6.5	Study visits and final conference		not open	sensitive personal data					Excel list	.xls		Annette Heiss (SUBMARINER Network)